

Kaniadakis Deformed Distribution and Statistics of Non-Linear Kinematics and Function-Inverse Function Pairs

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Kaniadakis (1) has introduced a statistics of non-linear kinematics based on a generalized Fokker-Planck type equation. He introduces a function:

$$K = S_k - 1/T (E - uN) \quad ((1))$$

where: $S_k = - \int \int \text{phase space} \, df \ln(k(f(x))) \quad ((2))$

Here $f(x)$ is the distribution with $x = 1/T(e-u)$, T being the temperature and u the chemical potential. “ k ” is a function related another function G of f_1 and f_2 , where $G(f, f')$ is related to the transition rate.

For Maxwell-Boltzmann two body scattering, k is the identity function. Kaniadakis condition for “equilibrium” is: $d/df K = 0$. He further postulates that: $S_k = \int \int \text{phase} \, df \, [\ln k](af)$. Here $\ln k(af) = \ln(k(f(x)))$, with $\ln k$ being a new function of f , in particular a generalized log function $1/2k (f^k - f'^k)$. The equilibrium solution satisfying $dK/df = 0$ is $\exp k(x)$ where $\exp k$ is the generalized log function. In performing dK/df , $-1/T (E - uN)$ is written as: $-1/T \int \int \text{phase} \, f \, f(e-u) (e-u)$ so it appears as a “constraint”.

In an earlier note, we argued that in Maxwell-Boltzmann statistical mechanics, one often sees the maximization of entropy subject to the energy constraint i.e.

$$d/df [- f \ln(f) - b_1 (e-u)f] = 0 \quad ((3)) \quad \text{This is solved to obtain: } f = \exp(-1/T (e-u))$$

We argue, however, that an f which is the inverse of \ln is being found with the argument of f being $1/T(e-u)$. Then, one immediately has a solution. We argue in this note, that the same thought process is occurring in the Kaniadakis approach. In other words:

$$dK/df = 0 = d/df [df \ln(k(f)) - 1/T ((e-u) f] \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one finds a function $\ln(k)$ which is the inverse of f so $\ln(k(f)) = (e-u)$.

The generalized log i.e. $\ln-k = 1/2k (f^k - f'^k)$ is already known from mathematics. For $k \rightarrow 0$, it becomes the regular log. Thus, one need only find its inverse function to obtain the equilibrium distribution. In Kaniadakis theory, it is postulated that $\ln(k(f))$ is the same as $\ln-k(af)$. Here we consider $a=1$.

Kaniadakis Theory Based on a Generalized Fokker-Planck Type of Equation

The basis of the Kaniadakis maximization approach depends on the development of a function $K(f)$ which in turn depends on a generalized Fokker-Planck type equation, so we present a very brief summary here. First, however, we examine $K(f)$.

$K(f) = S_k - 1/T(E-u)$, where $S_k = \int \int \text{phase space } df \ln(k(f))$ [where f is the distribution and k an unknown function related to kinematics] so it is $K(f)$ which is critical. The equilibrium solution follows from $dK/df = 0$. Ultimately, what seems to happen, however, is that K itself becomes zero, so $S_k = 1/T(E-u)$ at equilibrium. This is identical to the Maxwell-Boltzmann case where one maximizes $A = - \int f \ln(f) - 1/T \int (e-u) f$ to obtain $f = \exp(-1/T(e-u))$ which is normalized. It turns out that this solution leads to $A = 0$. Thus, one could have immediately chosen a solution such that:

$$\ln(f) = -1/T (e-u) \quad \text{where } f \text{ and } \ln \text{ are inverse functions.}$$

In fact, in the MB case, one does not need the idea of maximizing entropy subject to a constraint to find f . One may use: $f_1 f_2 = f_3 f_4$ for a two particle scattering situation which leads to equilibrium. Here $T_{12} = T_{34}$ so there is time reversal balance. Taking the \ln of $f_1 f_2 = f_3 f_4$ leads to $\ln(f_1) + \ln(f_2) = \ln(f_3) + \ln(f_4)$ which is of the form of a conservation equation. Thus, if f is a function of the conserved quantity, say energy, then \ln and f should be inverse functions.

An identical situation seems to occur for:

$$dK/df = 0 = d/df \int \int \text{phase space } df \ln(k(f)) - 1/T \int (e-u) f \quad ((5a))$$

If f is a function of $1/T(e-u)$, then $\ln(k)$ being the inverse of f immediately yields a solution. Thus, the problem is one of function-inverse function pairs. Let us first briefly, however, consider how K is obtained in the first place in (1).

Article (1) starts with a transition rate for a two particle collision from f, f' to f_1 and f_1' given by:

$$T() G(f, f') G(f_1, f_1') \quad ((5b))$$

where G is a function related to availability and f the distribution and T is a transition type function (related to cross sections etc).

Next, it is assumed that: $G(f, f') / G(f, f') = k(f) / k(f')$ ((5c)) where k is an unknown function.

It should be pointed out that from the function-inverse function arguments made above, $\ln(k)$ is the inverse of f for the equilibrium solution and f a function of $1/T(e-u)$. Thus, it seems that $k = \exp(1/T(e-u))$ regardless of the form of f equilibrium. This implies that $k(f) / k(f') = \exp(1/T(e-e'))$ for any equilibrium f .

Article (1) then uses a Kramer's relationship:

$$df/dt = \text{Integral } dv' [T(t,x, v \rightarrow v') - T(t,x, v' \rightarrow v)] \quad ((5d))$$

Here T is a transition rate, which considers the difference in transitions out of v and into v, where v is the velocity, to find the change in f(v) in time.

$$T \text{ is then written as: } T = w(t,x, v-v') G(f,f') \quad ((5e))$$

Article (1) then makes assumptions about the rate of reactions and the dominant v to v' transitions (assumed to be small) in order to make use of Taylor series expansions. We leave the details to (1). In the algebra, $\ln[G(f,f') / G(f',f)]$ appears leading to $\ln(k(f)) - \ln(k(f'))$ from ((5c)).

The final result is:

$$df/dt - d/dv \{ D(v) G(f) d/dv [1/T(KE + V(x) - u) + \ln(k(f))] \} = 0 \quad ((5f)) \text{ where } KE+V(x) \text{ is energy and } u \text{ the chemical potential.}$$

This is written as:

$$df/dt + d/dv [D G(f) d/dv dK(f)/df] = 0 \quad ((5g)) \text{ where } D \text{ is a diffusion constant and } G(f)=G(f,f)$$

$$\text{Where } K = -\text{Integral phase space } \text{Integral } df \ln(k(f)) - \text{Integral phase space } \text{Integral } df f \frac{1}{T(e-u)}. \quad ((5h))$$

It seems that taking d/df of K in ((5g)) is the inverse operation of $\text{Integral } df$ in ((5h)). It also seems one may directly find a solution of ((5f)) for df/dt=0 (i.e. "equilibrium or stationary situation") if:

$$1/T(KE+V(x)-u) + \ln(k(f)) = 0 \quad ((5i))$$

This implies $\ln(k)$ and f should be inverse function pairs if f is a function of $1/T(e-u)$.

The Generalized Logarithm

In the arguments presented above, it is suggested one needs a function, inverse function pair in order to find an equilibrium solution which is equivalent to $dK/df=0$. Kaniadiakis has suggested, as a postulate, using the generalized log function:

$$\text{Ln}k = 1/2k (f^k - f^{-k}) \text{ i.e. he uses } \ln(k(f)) = \text{Ln}k(af) \text{ Here we consider } a=1. \quad ((6))$$

Thus, to find the equilibrium distribution $f(e-u)$ one need only find the inverse of $\ln k$ which is readily known from math (and also presented in (1)) i.e.

$$\exp k(x) = [\sqrt{1+k^2x^2} + kx]^{1/k}$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest a solution of the equilibrium distribution in Kaniadakis' statistics of nonlinear kinematics is the inverse of the function $\ln(k)$. Here \ln is the normal natural logarithm and k is a function related to the nonlinear kinematics. In (1), a specific solution for k is not found, rather it is postulated that $\ln(k(f)) = \ln k(f(af))$ where a is a constant (we consider $a=1$) and $\ln k$ is the generalized logarithm (from mathematics) i.e. ((6)). We suggest that this idea of function-inverse function pair already exists in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case where \ln and f are inverse functions.

References

Kaniadakis, G. Nonlinear Kinetics Underlying Generalized Statistics. 2018
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0103467.pdf>